

Studies on Aminosugars. I. Synthesis of Optically Active N-Aryl-D-Glucoheptosaminonitriles

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(+) and (-) -N-aryl-D-glucoheptosaminonitriles have been prepared by condensing D-glucosecyanhydrin with bases like aniline, *o*-, *m*-, *o*-toluidines, *p*-anisidine, benzidine, α -naphthylamine and haloanilines. The condensation with *o*-toluidine gave two isomeric products, the structure of which have been supported by IR spectra study.

Very limited information for aminosugars in plants is available. It was therefore intended to carry out further work in this field. Aminosugars can be obtained by the hemihydrogenation of respective nitriles. The nitriles were prepared by the action of hydrogencyanide on (i) 2-acetamido-2-deoxyaldoses¹, (ii) on Schiff's base type compounds²⁻⁴ and on glycosylamine⁵⁻⁷. We have attempted the synthesis of (+) and (-) N-aryl-D-glucoheptosaminonitriles of the type of HO.CH₂(CHOH)₄-CH-NH.R by condensing cyanhydrin

of D-glucose with amines, where R = phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-bromophenyl, *p*-iodophenyl, α -naphthyl, 4-4'-diphenyl, *p*-sulphophenyl and *p*-sulphonamidophenyl.

The reaction was carried out at about 6.5 to 7.2 pH. The yield of nitriles varies from 5 to 60%. The formation of cyanohydrin at pH 7.2 has been confirmed by the method suggested by Walter Militzer⁸. The yield of cyanohydrin is 70%. It is conclusively confirmed that Schiff's base formation does not take place under this experimental condition. When *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, *p*-iodoaniline, sulphanilic acid and sulphanilamide reacts with cyanohydrin of D-glucose, the mixture of nitrile, glycosylamine and 1-arylamino-1-deoxyfructose is obtained from which individual separation was difficult. However, *p*-chloro and *p*-iodo-D-glucoheptosaminonitriles were successfully separated by repeated fractional crystallisation in absolute alcohol. On the otherhand, N-phenyl, N-*o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl, N-anisyl, N- α -naphthyl, N'-N-4-4'-diphenyl-D-glucoheptosaminonitriles formation take place without the formation of glycosylamine and 1-arylamino-1-deoxyfructose as side product. This was supported by the reaction of D-glucose and amines with potassium cyanide and acetic acid as well as in absence of potassium cyanide under similar conditions. The nitriles so obtained are sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform and acetone but soluble in pyridine. They are crystallised from absolute alcohol and their optical rotations were taken in pyridine (recorded in table). In the condensation of *o*-toluidine with cyanohydrin of D-glucose, two isomeric nitriles are obtained which have been supported by IR spectra study.

(A)

(B)

N-Aryl-D-glucoheptosaminonitriles.

Infrared spectra study: The IR spectra of glycosylamine and its derivatives were studied by Butler and coworker and Legay⁹⁻¹¹. A very weak cyanide band is obtained at 2250 cm^{-1} . The two possible isomeric structure predicted for nitriles are (A) and (B) in which cyano group is trans or cis with respect to hydroxyl group at carbon-2 respectively. The alcohol soluble product obtained by condensing *o*-toluidine with D-glucosecyanohydrin gives a broad and intense band at 3360 cm^{-1} of -NH and -OH combined alongwith a weak cyanide band at 2250 cm^{-1} predicting structure (A). On the otherhand in alcohol insoluble product the -NH and -OH bands are distinct at 3280 cm^{-1} and 3400 cm^{-1} respectively alongwith a negligible cyanide intensity and hence predicting structure (B). The weakening of cyanide intensity may be due to vicinity of -OH group which is comparatively less effective in structure (A). Similarly structure (A) predominates in the condensation of aniline, *p*-iooaniline, *p*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine and structure (B) in *p*-anisidine. The IR spectra were taken in nujol using Beckman IR-5 spectrophotometer.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Preparation of (+) and (-) N-o-tolyl-D-glucoheptosaminonitriles*: D-glucose $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +52.5$ (anhydrous 18.0 g) was taken in alcohol (95%, 50 ml) and potassium cyanide (6.5 g) in water (10 ml.) was added immediately followed by glacial acetic acid (6 ml.) and the contents were stirred till clear solution was obtained. *o*-Toluidine (10.7 g) was then added with constant stirring and the reaction mixture was kept for 24 hrs at 25°–30°. The contents were poured in crushed ice and allowed to stand for few hours. The product (13.55 g) was treated with hot ethanol (95%, 50 ml) so as to get 1.85 g. of the less soluble product. The more soluble product was concentrated under vacuum and gave 11.5 g. of the product which was recrystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in the table.

The condensation of D-glucose cyanohydrin with aniline gave the product m.p. 167–68° (Miller and Plockel⁵ quoted 168°), other bases were similarly condensed.

(b) *Preparation (+) N-N', 4-4'-diphenyl bis-D-glucoheptosaminonitrile*: The condensation with benzidine was carried out using procedure (a) in 200 ml. alcohol. The product was crystallised from alcohol in microplates.

TABLE

Optically active N-aryl-D-glucosaminonitrites of the type HO-CH₂(CHOH)₄CN-NH.R

Sr. No.	R =	Cond. time, in hr.	Formula	% yield	m.p. °C	c	[α] _D ²⁰ l = 1		% of N		% of C		% of H	
							pyridine	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1.	Phenyl	24	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₂	45	167-68	2.00	-140.00	9.95	9.93	55.42	55.33	6.43	6.38	
2.	o-Tolyl (+)	24	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₂	06	174-75	1.16	+125.00	9.61	9.46	56.81	56.75	6.80	6.76	
3.	o-Tolyl (-)	24	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₂	39	153	1.90	-97.36	9.56	9.46	56.64	56.75	6.50	6.76	
4.	m-Tolyl	24	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₂	60	143	1.20	-62.75	9.32	9.46	56.55	56.75	6.70	6.76	
5.	p-Tolyl	24	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₂	60	139-40	1.33	+146.60	9.30	9.46	56.49	56.75	6.42	6.76	
6.	p-Anisyl	24	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₂	62	139-40	1.99	-135.70	8.88	8.97	53.92	53.84	6.54	6.41	
7.	α-Naphthyl	90	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₂	06	184	2.29	+122.30	8.50	8.44	61.60	61.45	6.38	6.02	
8.	4-4'-Diphenyl	90	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₀ N ₄	18	300	0.05	+100.00	9.84	9.97	55.30	55.52	5.98	6.05	
9.	p-Iodophenyl	36	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₂ I	06	147-48	0.91	-38.46	6.54	6.66	38.41	38.23	4.18	4.17	
10.	p-Chlorophenyl	24	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	04	171	0.55	+145.40	8.79	8.85	49.10	49.28	5.25	5.37	

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